

TYPOLOGY OF EVENT TOURIS AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL IN ORDER TO STRENGTHEN LOCAL ECONOMIC CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Event tourism as a direction has recently become increasingly popular, its essence is in participation or visiting a certain event within the framework of a ready-made tour. The most significant are major events in the sports segment, fashion shows, exhibitions and festivals, music concerts, as well as holidays that have national affiliation. The article considers event tourism. Tourism is an intensively developing sector of the world economy. The most significant events of event tourism are major events in the sports world, fashion shows, exhibitions and festivals, music concerts. The authors reviewed international and domestic experience in organizing events of an event nature.

Keywords: Tourism, even tourism, event tourism management, local development, economic development.

Event tourism is a type of tourism in which tourist trips are timed to coincide with specific events. Every country hosts events of cultural, historical, and sporting significance. When creating a tourist attraction that does not have its own historical event, one is created specifically for that purpose. This means that a campaign is created and conducted to increase the significance of the tourist product, aimed at attracting a large number of visitors and, consequently, generating cash flow from tourists who want to visit certain places not only to see the sights, but also to take part in joint celebrations with local residents.

Event tourism has great economic significance, as it stimulates activity across the entire tourism industry during the period in which it takes place. Supply is significantly lower than consumer demand. During preparations for an event, one can observe a revival of local cultural traditions and customs, increased patriotism, and the development of folk art.

Let us consider the classification of events that attract tourists to countries:

- cultural celebrations (carnivals, festivals, religious events),
- political and state events (international forums, summits, official visits, elections),
- events in the field of education and science (seminars, conferences, award ceremonies),
- events in the field of art and entertainment (exhibitions, fairs, business forums, concerts, award ceremonies),
- sports events and competitions (Olympics, championships, competitions),
- social events (national holidays) [1].

It is evident that a product based on event tourism is closer in nature to the experience economy. The key factor in obtaining experiences is not the results, as in the provision of services, but the emotional effect,

mood, and pleasure that combine to form a general impression and then a memory. According to scientists in this field, event tourism is at the forefront of the development of the experience economy, as it involves participation in an event, while the basis of the attractiveness of the tourist product is future impressions and memories, and these impressions can be obtained not from a long trip, but from a 2–3-day festival [2].

The popularity of event tourism in the modern world is linked to its main advantages: it is not seasonal, it is held regularly, it offers an inexhaustible range of themes, and it has the potential to generate high revenues. The author notes that the main disadvantage is the unpredictability of demand. Agreeing in general with many authors who have conducted research in the field of event tourism, it can only be noted that with proper planning, events generate a relatively quick return on investment.

Many authors also emphasize the uniqueness of event tourism, its high level of integration and embeddability in the socio-cultural landscape, which makes it an important tool for achieving mutual understanding and cooperation [1,2].

It is interesting to highlight event tourism not as a type of tourism, but as a block that is formed on the basis of various types of tourism: ecological, cultural, sports, and business. A block here is understood as a specific (free, unstructured) group of types of tourism united by some form of activity. At the same time, event tourism can be divided into business and entertainment.

Thus, event tourism is understood as tourist activities related to various significant public events, as well as rare natural phenomena that attract large numbers of compatriots and tourists from foreign countries with their uniqueness, exoticism, and originality.

In order to gain a more detailed understanding of the essence of event tourism, we have attempted to classify it (see Table 1).

Classification of event tourism		
Type of tourism	Events	
Cultural tourism	National festivals and holidays	European carnivals
		Reconstruction of historical events
		Ethnographic festivals
		Country, region, city days
		Religious events and dates
	Cultural exhibitions	Biennale of Arts
		Art auctions
		Food festivals
		Flower festivals and exhibitions
	Theater, film, and music events	Concerts by world-famous celebrities
		Film and theater festivals
		Music festivals and music competitions
	Fashion world events	Fashion shows
Beauty contests		
Sports tourism	Olympics and international competitions	
	Auto racing, rallies, international technical exhibitions	
	Air shows	
	Sailing regattas, rowing competitions	
	Horse racing, equestrian shows	
	Winter sports competitions	
	Hunting and fishing tournaments	
Business tourism	Exhibitions	
	Conferences	
	Forums, congresses	

According to Table 1, event tourism combines the main types of tourism (cultural, sports, and business) and includes a wide range of events, from national festivals and holidays to competitions and master classes [3].

In recent decades, historical reenactment (theatricalization) based on artistic interpretation of real life or historical events has become one of the foundations for the development of event tourism. According to data presented on an English-language website dedicated to reenactments, there are more than 250 historical reenactment groups in the world. Historical reenactment is an educational or entertainment activity in which people recreate certain aspects of a historical event or period, as well as the material and spiritual culture of an era and region, using archaeological, visual, and written sources [4].

Festival events are developing at the regional level. The regions of Kazakhstan have not yet actively joined the process of creating their own tourist events, which cannot be said about large metropolitan cities, which have become more active on the basis of the unique intangible cultural heritage of peoples, including folk festivals, folklore, historical past, as well as places associated with the life and work of outstanding figures of science and art.

The potential of festival tourism, including military-historical tourism, is quite significant. Due to historical specifics, almost every country has resources for its development. It has been established that the resource base for festival military-historical tourism consists mainly of museum-historical complexes and fortifications. Global and domestic experience in organizing festivals indicates broad prospects for the development of festival tourism based on engagement with historical events.

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